

Accessible Learning Labs

Hardware and Software Requirements

Due to the labs' hosted nature, users require only a computer connected to the internet and a web browser (Chrome, Firefox, Safari, etc). More specifically, there are no hardware requirements, other than a computer, to utilize the labs. The completed lab materials, which include lecture slides, videos, quizzes, and interactive activities, are available on our project website located at: <https://all.rit.edu>.